

Spectral and kinetic studies of thermal decomposition of complexes of biologically active glutathione with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions^ψ

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The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of reduced glutathione (GSH) of general composition [M(L)(X)].nH₂O (where LH₂ = GSH; X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻/CH₃CO₂⁻, and n = 1-2) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, infrared spectra, electronic spectra and thermal studies. The complexes were found to be monomer and involved coordination through cystein sulphur and carboxylate oxygen giving tetrahedral geometry. From thermogravimetric (TG) studies, order of the reaction, mass loss and apparent activation energy have been calculated and from differential thermal analytical studies, heat of reaction has been measured. Thermodynamic activation parameters have been calculated.

The coordination chemistry of glutathione is of vital importance as it serves as a model system for the binding of metal ions by larger peptide and protein molecules. This is important constituent of enzyme, protein and is present in many parts of the biological system¹. Glutathione (reduced), a biological reducing agent in thiol dependent enzyme reactions², has recently been reported to have anticancer activity³⁻⁶, and glutathione enzyme was chosen as target molecules in antineoplastic chemotherapy treatment⁷. Its metal complexes are involved in the toxicology of several metals^{8,9}. Because of the presence of potential binding sites, glutathione exhibits a wide range of stereo chemistries on complexation with metal ions¹⁰⁻¹². Since its coordination chemistry is complicated that requires results from a combination of various techniques. We report herein the synthesis, spectral characterization, potentiometric studies and thermal studies of biologically active glutathione with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions.

Results and discussion

All the complexes were found to be white crystalline substances, non-hygroscopic and insoluble in common organic solvents. Satisfactory results of elemental analysis (Table 1) and spectral studies revealed that the complexes were of good purity. Various attempts to obtain the single crystals have so far been unsuccessful.

Potentiometric studies :

The nature of the equilibria and the stability constants of complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with glutathione have been

studied pH-metrically at different ionic strength, temperature and solvents¹³. The stability constant of Zn^{II} complex is greater than Cd^{II} complex. Species distribution curves of complexes of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with glutathione have been plotted as a function of pH at constant temperature of 25 ± 0.5° and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength, using the program SPE. The SPE curves give the percentage of various species existing in metal glutathione equilibria at different pH values. The SPE distribution curve showed that complexation starts at pH 3.40 and becomes maximum (~65-70%) in the pH range 3.5-4.5 and after that decreases to zero at pH ~ 11.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligand and metal complexes are given in Table 2. The results indicate that the glutathione (GSH) shows a strong band at 2525 cm⁻¹ due to ν(SH), which is absent in the spectra of the complexes indicating the deprotonation and coordination of the thiol group. This has been confirmed by the appearance of ν(M-S) band at 310-300 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes suggesting the binding of metal through sulphur¹⁴. In glutathione, the band at 1713 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the -COOH group of the glycine residue, which is absent in all the complexes, indicating the binding of -COOH group of glycine with metal ions in all the complexes¹⁵. The doublet peaks, appearing at 3350(s) cm⁻¹ and 3251(s) cm⁻¹ are due to symmetric stretching vibrations of the peptide group¹⁶ merged into a single band in all complexes in the region 3400-3200 cm⁻¹. The N-H stretching frequency at 3125-

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Analytical data of metal complexes

Complexes	Yield (%)	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	S	M
(1) [Zn(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O (C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₇ SClZn)	68	White	28.17 (28.29)	4.00 (4.01)	9.81 (9.90)	7.47 (7.54)	15.38 (15.41)
(2) [Zn(L)(CH ₃ CO ₂)].2H ₂ O (C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₁₀ SZn)	62	White	30.89 (30.92)	4.65 (4.72)	8.83 (9.02)	6.72 (6.87)	13.80 (14.04)
(3) [Cd(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O (C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₇ SClCd)	65	White	25.21 (25.47)	3.37 (3.61)	8.76 (8.91)	6.59 (6.79)	23.62 (23.85)
(4) [Cd(L)(NO ₃)].H ₂ O (C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₁₀ SCd)	64	White	24.01 (24.11)	3.37 (3.42)	11.09 (11.25)	6.33 (6.43)	22.25 (22.50)

Table 2. Infrared spectral data (cm⁻¹) of the ligand and metal complexes

Compd.	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{SH})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{X})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$	Other assignments
(1) GSH(LH ₂)		3350(s), 3251(s), 3125-2900(s)	1713(s), 1665(w), 1540(m), 1395(s)	2525(s)			
(2) [Zn(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	3502	3274(s,b), 2929(s)	1635(s,b), 1513(m), 1385(s)		310(m), 275(vs)	302	
(3) [Zn(L)(CH ₃ CO ₂)].2H ₂ O	3498	3302(s,b), 2938(s)	1630(s,b), 1528(m), 1400(s), 1310(m)			308	
(4) [Cd(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	3514	3288(s,b), 2941(s)	1631(s,b), 1522(m), 1396(s)		312(m), 250(vs)	310	
(5) [Cd(L)(NO ₃)].H ₂ O	3486	3328(s,b), 2923(s)	1642(s,b), 1533(m), 1402(s)			307	1275(s), 702(w) $\nu[\text{M}-\text{NO}_3]$

2900 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand in a hydrogen bonded NH₃⁺ in zwitter ion ⁻OOC-C-NH₃⁺ of the amino acid moiety does not show any considerable shift in complexes, indicating the non participation of this N-H group¹⁷. All complexes showed broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ from water molecules. This band is absent in the ligand. The band at 1665 cm⁻¹ in the GSH is assigned to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching of the peptide bonds. This band has been shifted to lower frequency at 1640 cm⁻¹ which indicates the coordination of the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group with metal atom^{15,16}.

The C=O and C-O stretching frequency at 1540(m) cm⁻¹ and 1395(s) cm⁻¹ in glutathione, are assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ modes of the carboxylate group and these band shows considerable shift in all the complexes¹⁸.

The acetate complex has band at 1630(s) cm⁻¹ and 1400(s) cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CO}_2)$ fundamental stretching bands, respectively, which are in agreement with the acetate group being monodentate. Because the difference Δ

$[\Delta = \nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2) - \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CO}_2)]$ is 1621-1405 = 216 cm⁻¹. The band at 1405 cm⁻¹ is due to the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CO}_2)$ mode of both acetate and L²⁻ ligand¹⁵.

The nitrate complex having two bands at 1275 cm⁻¹ and 1387 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_1 and ν_4 of the nitrate groups with a separation of 112 cm⁻¹, explains monodentate coordination^{15,19}. A weak band at 702 cm⁻¹ assignable to the ν_3 mode is a further support for the presence of a terminally bonded nitrate group.

Electronic spectra :

The reflectance spectral results showed that the transition at around 250 nm in all the complexes has been assigned to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, charge transfer due to the carbonyl to the metal²⁰. Bands at 330 nm region of the spectra of the complexes, as a consequence of internal $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, and those in the 450 nm region to the S (σ) \rightarrow M(II) charge transfer bands²¹.

Thermal analyses :

Thermal data of the complexes are given in Table 3. The correlations between the different decomposition steps

Table 3. Thermoanalytical data (TG, DTA) of M(II)-glutathione complexes

Complexes	Step	TG	DTA	Thermal	Mass-loss	Assignments	Metallic residue
	no.	range/K	Max/K	effect	obs. (calc.) %		
[Zn(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	I	321–368	345	Endo	4.20 (4.24)	H ₂ O	
	II	472–500	488	Endo	22.45 (22.50)	CH ₄ NO ₂	ZnO
	III	754–848	807	Exo	49.68 (49.75)	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	
[Zn(L)(CH ₃ CO ₂)].2H ₂ O	I	331–364	352	Endo	7.70 (7.75)	H ₂ O	
	II	485–512	497	Endo	25.10 (25.55)	C ₃ H ₇ NO ₄	ZnO
	III	756–842	806	Exo	52.71 (52.61)	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	
[Cd(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	I	327–367	348	Endo	3.78 (3.82)	H ₂ O	
	II	464–495	481	Endo	20.15 (20.27)	CH ₄ NO ₂ Cl	CdO
	III	783–840	798	Exo	48.32 (48.18)	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	
[Cd(L)(NO ₃)].H ₂ O	I	340–369	359	Endo	16.00 (16.07)	H ₂ O + NO ₂ + O	
	II	471–506	495	Endo	11.70 (11.85)	CH ₃ NO ₂	CdO
	III	740–853	801	Exo	46.00 (45.81)	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	

of the complexes with the corresponding weight losses are discussed in terms of the proposed formula of the complexes.

The [Zn(L)(Cl)].H₂O complex with the general formula [Zn(C₁₀H₁₅N₃O₆SCI).H₂O] is thermally decomposed in three successive decomposition steps. The first estimated mass loss of 4.20% within the temperature range (321–368 K) may be attributed to the loss of water molecule (calculated mass loss = 4.24%). The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 345 K (maximum peak temp.). The second step occurs within the temperature range 472–500 K with the estimated mass loss 22.45% (calculated mass loss = 22.50%) are reasonably accounted for the decomposition of the HCl + NH₃ + CO₂. The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 488 K. The third step of decomposition occurs within the temperature range 754–848 K with an estimated mass loss of 49.68% (calculated mass loss = 49.75%), which corresponds to the loss of C₉H₁₁N₂O₃S molecule leaving ZnO residue. The DTA curve gives exothermic peak at 807 K (maximum peak temp.).

The [Zn(L)(CH₃CO₂)].2H₂O complex with the general formula [Zn(C₁₂H₁₈N₃O₈S)].2H₂O is thermally decomposed in three successive decomposition steps within the temperature range 331–842 K. The first decomposition step of estimated mass loss 7.70% within the temperature range 331–364 K may be attributed to the liberation of water molecules (calculated mass loss = 7.75%). The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 352 K. The second step found within the estimated mass loss 25.10% (calculated mass loss = 25.55%) which is responsibly accounted for the decomposition of C₃H₇NO₄ molecule.

The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 497 K. The third step found in the TG range 756–842 K, which is responsibly accounted for the decomposition of rest of the ligand molecules (C₉H₁₃N₂O₄S) with a final residue ZnO. The DTA curve shows exothermic peak at 806 K (maximum peak temp.).

In [Cd(L)(Cl)].H₂O complex with the general formula Cd[(C₁₀H₁₅N₃O₆SCI)].H₂O was thermally decomposed again in three steps. The first estimated mass loss of 3.78% (calculated mass loss = 3.82%) within the temperature range 327–367 K may be attributed to the liberation of water molecule. The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 348 K. The second estimated mass loss 20.15% (calculated mass loss = 20.27%) in the temperature range 464–495 K may be attributed to the loss of CH₄NO₂Cl. The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 481 K. The third step of decomposition occurs within the temperature range 783–840 K with an estimated mass loss of 48.32% (calculated mass loss = 48.18%), which corresponds to the loss of C₉H₁₁N₂O₃S molecule of the ligand leaving CdO. The DTA curve shows exothermic peak at 798 K (maximum peak temp.).

The [Cd(L)(NO₃)].H₂O complex with the formula [Cd(C₁₀H₁₅N₄O₁₀S)].H₂O was thermally decomposed in three successive decomposition steps. The first estimated mass loss 16.00% (calculated mass loss = 16.07%) within the temperature range 340–369 K can be attributed to the liberation of water molecule along with NO₂ + O molecule. The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at maximum peak temperature 359 K. The second step occurs within the temperature range 471–506 K with an esti-

Table 4. Thermodynamic activation parameters

Complex	Order (<i>n</i>)	<i>E</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)	<i>A</i> (s ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>H</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> * (kJ mol ⁻¹)
[Zn(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	1	45.37	2.58 × 10 ⁵	-138.02	43.78	70.20
[Zn(L)(CH ₃ CO ₂)].2H ₂ O	1	63.00	9.02 × 10 ⁵	-128.91	61.37	87.97
[Cd(L)(Cl)].H ₂ O	1	77.02	1.10 × 10 ¹¹	-21.60	76.41	77.80
[Cd(L)(NO ₃)].H ₂ O	1	39.43	6.11 × 10 ¹²	-184.03	38.90	76.51

mated mass loss 11.70% (calculated mass loss = 11.85%), which is reasonably accounted for the loss of CH₃NO₂ molecule. The DTA curve gives endothermic peak at 495 K. The third step occurs within the temperature range 740–853 K with an estimated mass loss 46.00% (calculated mass loss = 45.81%) which is reasonably accounted for the loss of rest of the ligand molecule, leaving CdO. The DTA curve gives exothermic peak at 801 K.

Kinetic analysis :

The kinetic analysis parameters such as activation energy (*E**), enthalpy of activation (Δ*H**), entropy of activation (Δ*S**) and free energy change of decomposition (Δ*G**) were evaluated graphically by employing the Coats-Redfern relation²² (1),

$$\log [-\log (1 - \alpha)/T^2] = \log [AR/\theta E^*(1 - 2RT/E^*)] - E^*/2.3RT \quad (1)$$

where α is the mass loss up to the temperature *T*, *R* is the gas constant, *E** is the activation energy in J mol⁻¹, θ is the heating rate and (1-2*RT*/*E**) ≅ 1. A plot of left hand side of eq. (1) against 1/*T* gives a slope from which *E** was calculated and *A* (Arrhenius constant) was determined from the intercept. The calculation of heat of reaction (Δ*H**) (Table 4) from the DTA curves were done by using

$$\Delta H^* = \Delta H (muv) 60.10^{-6} M/1000 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

where *M* is the molar mass of the complex. The entropy of activation (Δ*S**) and the free energy change of activation (Δ*G**) were calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta S^* = 2.303R[\log (Ah/kT)] \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T \Delta S^* \quad (3)$$

where *k* and *h* are the Boltzman and Plank's constant, respectively. The calculated values of *E**, *A*, Δ*S**, Δ*H** and Δ*G** for the decomposition steps are given in Table 4. The Δ*S** values were found to be negative, which indicate a more ordered activated state. The negative values of the entropies of activation are compensated by the values of the enthalpies of activation, leading to almost the same values for the free energies of activation.

Thus, on the basis of above physico-chemical data in conjunction with consideration of ring strain, tetrahedral (Fig. 1) seems to be likely for all the complexes.

Fig. 1. The proposed structure of [M(L)(X)].nH₂O complexes prepared where LH₂ = GSH and X⁻ = Cl⁻ (*n* = 1), NO₃⁻ (*n* = 1) and CH₃COO₂⁻ (*n* = 2).

Experimental

The complexes were analyzed for C, H, N, S. Metal contents were estimated on a AA-640-13 Shimadzu flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer in solutions prepared by decomposing the complexes in hot concentrated HNO₃. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer spectrum 2000 in KBr and polyethylene pellets. The electronic spectra (900–200) nm of the complexes in solid state were recorded on Jasco-Unidec-430B double beam spectrophotometer. Rigaku Model 8150 Thermoanalyser (Thermafex) was used for simultaneous recording of TG-DTA curves at a heating rate of 5/10° min⁻¹. For TG, the instrument was calibrated using calcium oxalate while for DTA, calibration was done using indium metal, both of which were supplied along with the instrument. A flat bed type Al-crucible was used with α-alumina (99% pure) as the reference material for DTA. The numbers of decomposition steps were identified using TG. The activation energy (*E**) and Arrhenius constant of the degradation process was obtained by Coats and Redfern method²². Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) salts and glutathione were procured from Aldrich and were used as received. Solvents used were of analytical grade and were purified by standard methods.

Synthesis of complexes :

Aqueous solution of zinc(II) salts (0.001 *M*) and cadmium(II) (0.001 *M*) salts were added with stirring to an aqueous solution of reduced glutathione (0.001 *M*) separately over 0.5 h. Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes were precipitated at pH 4.0 and 4.5 respectively. All the precipitates were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

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